

Table 1. Effect of hydrogels and moisture stress conditions on yield of wheat under soybean- wheat system during 2020

Treatment	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Biological yield (kg/ha)	Harvest index (%)
<i>Moisture stress condition</i>			
Irrigated	5745	13455	43.0
Rainfed	3522	9229	38.4
SEm±	276	630	1.8
CD (P=0.05)	1679	3835	NS
<i>Hydrogel application</i>			
Control	4654	11424	40.3
Seed treatment +SPG 1118	5015	12005	42.3
Seed treatment +P-hydrogel	4732	11479	41.2
Slurry application + SPG 1118	4754	11717	39.9
Slurry application + P-hydrogel	4676	11339	40.7
Soil application + SPG 1118	4381	11058	40.0
Soil application + P-hydrogel	4220	10372	40.8
SEm±	104	266	1.4
CD (P=0.05)	304	776	NS

CONCLUSION

Seed treatment of wheat with hydrogels using binders found promising in enhancing germination and productivity of crops. Thus cost incurred on hydrogels could be reduced and farmers can be easily adopted the technology.

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Nanoparticles in mitigating drought stress- A Review

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The main concern of today's agriculture is increasing crop productivity to feed the huge population of India. Crop yield is often affected by some biotic and abiotic factors, like climatic factors, agronomic factors, pests, nutrient availability of soil, etc. Stress is addressed as any adverse environmental condition that hampers plant growth. From the last few decades nanobiotechnology-based applications to mitigate stress attracted researcher's attention in this direction. Here, we have reviewed and discussed the enhancement of productivity in cereals, pulses, oilseeds, and fibre crops mitigating drought stress through the application of optimum concentration of nanoparticles (NPs).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dawood *et al.* (2019) reported that 0.1% TiO₂ NP treatment for 4 weeks in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) improved growth kinetics and leaf growth parameters. While 300 mg CuO NP and 500 mg ZnO NP /kg of soil through interaction with root-colonizing microbes reported to altering the plant growth and functions in wheat (Yang *et al.*, 2017). In Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.), 200 ml of silicon L⁻¹ of potassium silicate (K₂O3Si) kg⁻¹ of soil reported to increase leaf area index, specific leaf weight, chlorophyll content, total dry weight, and decrease in the shoot to root ratio and leaf

water potential (Ahmed *et al.*, 2010). In an experiment Dimkpa *et al.* (2019) observed 5 mg ZnO NP /kg soil improved grain N translocation, total K acquisition, grain yield but lowered total P acquisition. In Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) application of TiO₂ NP and SiO₂ NP @ 20 ppm individually stimulated growth and yield attributes where the response with SiO₂ NP was more pronounced (Ghorbanian *et al.*, 2017). 90 ppm chitosan nanoparticles (CS NP) when applied in barley at tillering, stem elongation and heading stages through foliar or soil application, increase in biomass, grain yield, relative water content, grain protein, leaf area, proline content, catalase, and superoxide dismutase were noticed by Behboudi *et al.* (2018) in drought stress. In pulses, lentils (*Lens culinaris* L.) responded when treated with silver nanoparticles (Ag NP) at a concentration of 10 µg ml⁻¹ which increased germination percentage, germination rate, radical length, and dry weight of radical (Seyed Saeid Hojjat, 2016). Linh *et al.* (2020) reported that 30 g seeds of the soybean (*Glycine max* L.) when soaked in 10 ml suspension of 50 mg l⁻¹ Fe NP for 30 minutes, plants responded with an increase in specific root length index (SRL), shoot dry weight, relative water content, drought tolerance index (DTI). 1 g l⁻¹ ZnO NP increased germination percentage, germination rate, radical length, fresh and dry weight of radicle but reduced seed residual dry and fresh weight in soybean (Sedghi *et al.*, 2013). 2 mg ml⁻¹ of Yttrium doping-stabilized α-Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles when applied with the nutrient solution in soil for 5 days, it increased growth rate of leaves, chlorophyll content and reduced level of H₂O₂ concentration and lipid peroxidation in Canola (*Brassica napus* L.) (Palmqvist *et al.*, 2017). According to Shallan *et al.* (2016), 50 ppm TiO₂ NP and 3200 ppm SiO₂ NP when applied through the foliar spray at the start of the flowering stage for 24 days in cotton (*Gossypium barbadense* L.) reported to increase pigments content, total soluble sugars, phenolics content, soluble proteins content, free amino acids, proline content, total reducing power, antioxidant enzyme activities and enhanced yield attributes. In Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) spraying of TiO₂ NP @ 10 mg l⁻¹ on shoots at initial seed filling stage for 3 days reported to enhance yield attributes, chlorophyll and carotenoids content in leaves, protein content, and decreased H₂O₂ accumulation and malondialdehyde content (Aghdam *et al.*, 2015).

CONCLUSION

The optimum dose of application of biosynthesized nanoparticles will lead to sustainable development in agriculture. Drought tolerance limit has increased with the application of nanoparticles through enhancing antioxidant system, nutrient uptake, photosynthesis, reduction of reactive oxygen species, reduction in leaf-water potential, and modulation of proteins. The effect of nanoparticles varies in crops,

depending on the mode of application, size, and concentration. So, it is the meantime to focus on dynamic interactions between crops and nanoparticles and their impact on the environment.

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